

Antimicrobial Activity of *Azadirachta Indica* Methanol and Ethanol Leaf Extract on *Escherichia Coli*

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Abstract-: This research investigates the antimicrobial activities of the leaf extract of Neem with a view to determining the quantity of extracts required to inhibit growth of *Escherichia coli*. Crude leaf extracts of Neem was made using Methanol and Ethanol. The phytochemical screening of the leaf reveals the presence of Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Tannins, Saponins, Alkaloids, Carbohydrates, Fat and Oil. Antibacterial activity of the extracts was determined using the Disc Diffusion method. The Ethanolic extract of the leaf showed the highest level of inhibition on *Escherichia coli* with a diameter of $19.50 \pm 0.3\text{mm}$ at a concentration of 400mg/ml . The antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli* isolates was attributed to the presence of these secondary metabolites. It is evident from the analysis presented that the extracts are efficient in inhibiting E-coli growth at higher concentrations. Therefore, *Azadirachta indica* is found to be a potential source of drugs for the treatment of E-coli infections.

Keywords: *Azadirachta indica*, Extract, Phytochemicals, Antimicrobial Activities, Traditional Medicine

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1.0 Introduction

Neem, *Azadirachta indica*, is a member of the mahogany family *Meliaceae* comprising fifty genera and five hundred species. The neem tree is thought to have originated from Assam in India and Burma where it is most widely used (Oparaeke, 2004). *Azadirachta indica* belongs to a large family of wood species with height ranging from 15.4m to 46.0m. The buttress measures from 0.1m to 1.14m in height; while the bark is relatively thin (Abdoulaye, 1997).

For centuries, the people of India cleaned their teeth with neem twigs, topically applied neem-leaf juice to treat skin disorders, took neem tea as tonic, and placed neem leaves in their beds, books, grain bins, cupboards, and closets to keep away troublesome bugs (National Research Council, 1992). Extracts from the tree had been

reported to relieve pains, fever, infections and other complaints.

In Nigeria, neem is locally known as “dogonyaro”, “darbejiya” in Hausa, “igi-oba” in Yoruba and “ogwu-akom” in Igbo. The neem tree used across all parts of the country as shelter-belts to control desertification. The tree remains leafy all year except during extreme drought, when the leaves fall. Neem trees are found generally in every state of the country growing wild. Although its abundance is of great economic value, its potential has not been fully exploited (Yakubu, 2006).

The discovery of antibiotics has been a blessing to the modern world. However, the uncontrolled and un-prescribed use of antibiotics has turned them into the enemy of human existence as microorganisms are becoming multidrug resistant. Given this, researchers and scientists agree that medicinal plants are a substantial alternative to this global crisis (Mulat M, 2019).

Medicinal plants are a common phenomenon in various continents and are also an essential source of different medicines (Al-Asmar *et al.*, 2017). Being a developing country, the use of medicinal plants in Nigeria is notable in many regions. Therefore, medicinal plants have become one of the leading choices for treating different injuries and diseases. A significant portion of the plant species has been recognized as valuable resources of natural antimicrobial compounds which can be used as an alternative for the treatment of bacterial infections (Subramari *et al.*, 2017). These are also the most suitable solution to the problems regarding antibiotic resistance, as they are cost-effective and have the least amount of side effects (Jeelani *et al.*, 2018).

Medicinal plants exhibit antibacterial activities due to the production of phytochemicals during the secondary metabolism of the plants (Barberi *et al.*, 2017). Plants are rich in a wide variety of secondary metabolites, including tannins, alkaloids, glycosides, and flavonoids. Plants produce these chemicals to protect themselves but it has been discovered that these compounds can protect humans against diseases (Augustine Airaodion *et al.*, 2019). These phytochemicals are known to exhibit anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antifungal activities (Barberi *et al.*, 2017). Reports suggest that phenolic and flavonoid compounds prevent diseases such as cancer, heart problems, cataracts, eye disorders, and Alzheimer's (Huyut, 2017). It is suggested that herbal extracts may be an effective alternative to antibiotics in order to cure common

recurrent diseases like diarrhea, skin disease, throat, or ear infection (Santhosh *et al.*, 2019).

Azadirachta indica (neem) belongs to the family *Meliaceae*. It originates from South Asia, but grows widely in India, Pakistan and other tropical and sub-tropical parts of the world (Bokhari *et al.*, 1985). The tree was introduced into Nigeria from Ghana, and it was first grown from the seeds in Maiduguri, in the then Bornu Province (now Borno State), Nigeria, in 1928 where Neem plant was nicknamed 'Dogon Yaro' after a Neem tree nursery caretaker in Maiduguri who happened to be the first Neem tree caretaker in Maiduguri (National Research Council, 1992). *Azadirachta indica*, is the Latin binomial for neem that is interpreted to mean the "Free Tree of India" (Rupani *et al.*, 2018). It is also known as the Holy and Untouchable Tree (Nosiba *et al.*, 2021).

Neem leaves have been reported to elicit various therapeutic effects such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimalarial, antiulcer, antihyperglycemic, antimutagenic, antidiabetic, anticarcinogenic, immunomodulatory and anticancer. Neem leaves and paste are also conventionally used to cure allergic skin reactions and treat smallpox and chickenpox (Hla *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, neem leaves have shown antifungal and antibacterial activities against various pathogenic microorganisms and antiviral effects for treating measles, Chikungunya, Vaccinia and Coxsackie B viruses (Gupta *et al.*, 2017).

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The emergence of antibiotic-resistant *Escherichia coli* strains is a public health concern, necessitating the development of alternative treatment options. *Azadirachta indica*, commonly known as neem, has been reported to possess significant antimicrobial activity against a range of bacterial pathogens. However, the potential of *Azadirachta indica* to inhibit growth of *E.coli* remains understudied. Therefore, this study investigates the anti-microbial property of *Azadirachta indica* against *E.coli*, with the aim of identifying its potential as a natural alternative option for *E.coli* infections treatment.

2.0 Material and Methods

2.1 Location:

The plant material of *Azadirachta indica* leaves was collected from the premises of Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano.

2.2 Sample Preparation and Extraction

Procedures:

The leaves of *Azadirachta indica* were spread and dried under shade for 4 days and pulverized with a mechanical grinder. Extraction was done separately with ethanol and methanol using the process described Table 1:

Table 1: Process of Extraction

Stage	Activity	Process
1	A 15 g sample of each powdered plant tissue was soaked for 24 h in 100 ml of ethanol and methanol.	Soaking
2	After 24 h, the extracts were filtered using a clean muslin cloth and filter paper.	Filtering
3	The filtrates were evaporated using a rotary evaporator.	Evaporation
4	All extracts were stored dry in sterile containers and	Drying and Refrigeration

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refrigerated until used for phytochemical analyses and antimicrobial testing.

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2022

2.3 Phytochemical Screening of the Plant Extracts

The phytochemical screening was carried out using the methods described by Farnsworth (1996), Harbone (1998) and Sofowora(1993).

i. Test for Alkaloids

A 0.2 g weight of each plant extracts was boiled with 5 ml of 2% hydrochloric acid in a water bath for 10 min. The mixture was filtered and 1 portion of each extract treated with 2drops of the following reagents as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Test for Alkaloids

S/No.	Reagent	Observation	Result
1	Mayer's Reagent:	A red precipitate	presence of alkaloids
2	Picric Acid (1%).	A yellow precipitate	presence of alkaloids

ii. Test for Flavonoids

A 0.2g weight of the extracts was heated with 10 ml of ethyl acetate in a boiling water-bath for 3 minutes. The mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was used for the Ammonium test. In this test, approximately 4ml of the filtrate was shaken with 1ml of diluted ammonia (1%). The layers were allowed to separate and a yellow color in the ammonia layer indicates the presence of flavonoid.

iii. Test for Glycosides:

This test was performed by weighing 2g of the extract and adding to 30ml of distilled water. The mixture was heated for 5 minutes in a boiling

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water bath, allowed to cool and filtered. Fehling's solution A and B were added to the filtrate until it turned alkaline when tested with red litmus paper. The alkaline mixture was heated in a boiling water bath for 2 minutes. A brick red precipitate indicates the presence of glycosides.

iv. Test for Saponins:

To conduct this test, 0.1 g of the extract was boiled with 5 ml of distilled water in a boiling water bath for 2 min. The mixture was filtered while still hot and allowed to cool. The filtrate was used for the following tests;

- i. Frothing test: Exactly 1ml of the filtrate was diluted with 4ml of distilled water. The mixture was vigorously shaken and then observed on standing for a stable froth.
- ii. Emulsion Test: To conduct this test, 2 drops of olive oil were added to 1ml of the filtrate. The mixture was shaken and observed for the formation of emulsion.

v. Test for Tannins:

In performing this test, 1g of the extract was boiled with 5ml of 45% ethanol (45ml of ethanol in 100ml of distilled water) for 5 minutes, the solution was filtered and the filtrate treated with ferric chloride solution. Using a pipette, 2 drops of ferric chloride was added to 1ml of the filtrate. A greenish black precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.

vi. Test for Fats and Oil.

About 0.2 g of the extract was pressed between filter paper and the paper observed. A control was also prepared by placing 2 drops of olive oil

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in filter paper. Translucency of the filter paper indicates the presence of fats and oil.

2.4 Microorganisms collection

The test organism (*Escherichia coli*) was clinically isolated, which were obtained from the Microbiological Laboratory of Infectious Disease Hospital (IDH), France Road, Sabongari, Kano State. They were stored on nutrient agar slants at 37°C as stock cultures until required for the study.

2.5 Media Preparation

All media used were prepared according to the manufacturer's directives. Nutrient Agar was prepared by suspending 23grams of the medium in one liter of distilled water and sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes and checked for sterility at 37°C for 24h. The Muller- Hinton Agar was prepared by suspending 38 grams of the medium in one liter of distilled water. It was mixed well and boiled for about one minute and sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes and checked for sterility at 37°C for 24h. The Nutrient Agar was used for plating out the organisms as well as storing them in slants while the Muller- Hinton Agar was used for sensitivity test.

2.6 Preparation of Crude Plant Extracts

A 2g of ethanolic and methanolic extract of *Azadiractha indica* of leaves was weighed out, using a Mettler balance, and then dissolved in 5ml of dimethyl sulphoxide in order to obtain concentrations of 400 mg/ml. Subsequently, the

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

400 mg/ml solution was serially diluted to obtain 200, 100, 50 and 25mg/ml concentrations.

2.7. Standardization of Inoculum

The standard solution (Barium Sulphate standard turbidity solution) was prepared as described by (Cheesbrough, 2000). A measure of 1ml of concentrated tetraoxosulphate VI acid (H₂SO₄) was added 99ml of distilled water after which 0.5g of Barium Chloride (BaCl₂.2H₂O) (BDH) was dissolved in water until the final volume of the solution reached 50ml mark. Then 0.6ml of Barium Chloride was then added to 99.4ml of the 1% H₂SO₄ solution and shake. The above processes resulted in turbid solution; a small volume of the turbid solution was taken in Testtube which was used for comparison during standardizing inoculums of the test organisms. (Cheesbrough, 2000)

For standardizing the inoculums, the procedure of (Bauer, 1966) was employed as follows: The test organisms were sub cultured on nutrient agar plates and incubated overnight. A Colony of the test organism was carefully picked using loop and transferred into a tube containing 2.0ml of normal saline until the turbidity of the suspension matches that of the standard turbidity solution. This is easier by viewing against a printed white sheet of paper. Where the inoculums are more turbid, a little more normal saline was added until its turbidity matched with the McFarland standard.

2.8 Determination of Antimicrobial Activity of Extracts

In the sensitivity test carried out, the activity of the extracts was evaluated by a modified disc

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diffusion method as described by Kirby (1996). During the test, Muller-Hinton agar plates were prepared. The surface of the agar was dried in a hot-air oven. Using sterile swab sticks, the agar plates were aseptically inoculated with the test organisms which were previously standardized by the Mcfarland standard to ensure even distribution of the test organism on the plates. With the aid of a sterile forceps and syringe needle, discs containing different concentration of the extract (400mg/ml, 200mg/ml, 100mg/ml and 50mg/ml) were impregnated firmly on the surface of inoculated plates. Control discs were also incorporated onto the inoculated plates, two controls were used these are: the positive and negative controls. The negative control discs were impregnated with the diluent i.e. DMSO while the positive control is a standard disc of chloramphenicol. Both discs were sufficiently spaced to prevent overlapping of the zones. The plates were then allowed for the pre-diffusion time of 15mins and they were incubated at 37°C for 24hours. The zones of inhibition formed were measured after incubation with the aid of a meter rule to determine the effectiveness of the extract on the organisms (Reagor *et al.*, 2002)

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1. Yield from Methanol and Ethanol Extractions

The ethanol leaves extract yielded a higher percentage than the methanol leaves extract according to table 4 below:

Table 4: Yield from the Ethanol and Methanol Extractions

Extract	Weight before extraction(g)	Weight after extraction(g)	Percentage Yield (%)

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

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<i>Methanol extracts</i>		
15	0.9	6.00
<i>Ethanol extracts</i>		
15	1.9	12.67

Source: Authors' Laboratory Analysis (2022)

3.2. Chemical Constituents in Ethanol and methanol of the Extracts.

The secondary metabolites tested were alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, Saponins, Tannins, Fats and oil. All secondary metabolites tested for were present in both ethanol and methanol extracts of *Azadiractha indica* leaves with exception to flavonoids which was absent in the ethanol extract of *Azadiractha indica*(Tables 5).

Table 5: Chemical Constituents in Ethanol and Methanol Extracts of *Azadiractha indica* leaves

Metabolites	Ethanol	Methanol
Alkaloids	+	+
Flavonoids	-	+
Glycosides	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Tannins	+	+
Fats and Oil	+	+

KEY: _ Absent; + Present

Source: Authors' Laboratory Analysis (2022)

3.3 Antibacterial activity of *Azadiractha indica* leaves on *Escherichia coli*.

Table 8 shows the inhibition zone diameter (IZD) measurement obtained for antibacterial activity of the leaf extracts against *Escherichia coli* (*E.coli*) responded slightly differently to

both ethanol and methanol extracts. The highest inhibition zone diameter was achieved with ethanol leaf extract of 19.50±0.3mm at a concentration of 400mg/ml followed by the activity of methanol leaf extract of 19.50±0.17mm at a concentration of 400mg/ml. The ethanol leaf extract at a concentration of 25mg/ml showed the least activity of 2.00mm. As shown in Table 8, the zone of inhibition for both ethanol and methanol extract decreases as the concentration of the extract also decreases. These results are also interpreted graphically in Figure1:

Table 8: Mean Size of inhibition zone (IZD) (mm) formed by different concentrations of Ethanol and Methanol Extracts of *Azadiractha indica* leaf.

	Concentration (mg/ml)				
Extr act	400	200	100	50	25
Ethan ol	19.50 ±0.2	15.00	7.00±0.2	2.00 ±0.2	2.00
Meth anol	19.00±0.3	13.50 ±0.1	11.50 ±0.2	9.00 ±0.3	4.00 ±0.2

Source : Authors' Fieldwork 2022.

Figure 1: Antibacterial activity of *Azadiractha indica* leaves.

Source: Authors' Fieldwork 2022.

5.0 Conclusion

Author Contribution

The phytochemical screening of the leaf extracts revealed the presence of Alkaloids, Glycosides,

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Saponins, Tannins, Fats and oil with exception to the methanol extracts where flavonoids are absent. These compounds have variously been reported to possess antimicrobial activity (Okeke *et al.*, 2001; Nethathe, 2011).

the increase in the concentration of extracts results to higher zones of inhibition.

Also, there are differences in phytochemical constituents extractable by the different solvents (ethanol and methanol) used. These differences seem to be reflected in the difference in spectrum and degree of antibacterial activity of extracts on the test organism.

Conclusively, this study shows that leaves of *Azadirachta indica* do contain phytochemicals and would be useful in treating *E.coli* infections, in high concentrations, could have potentially effective results. However, further research is necessary to identify the active elements in the plant that can be used to specifically target *E .Coli* before any real-world implementation and developments of treatments for the infection using *Azadirachta indica* can take place.

While comparing the ethanol and methanol leaf extracts, it was discovered that there is no significant difference in the antibacterial power of these extracts.

Conflict of Interest

The authors hereby declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

The inhibition diameters of the various extracts were also compared to that of a standard antibacterial, cholramphenicol and it was observed that although the extracts would inhibit the growth of *E. Coli*, it would be required in very high concentrations to kill off the bacteria permanently which is counter-productive as the end goal is to provide drugs in the lowest concentrations that would not have adverse effects on man while eliminating the bacteria.

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This research also shows that the plant extracts exhibited higher zones of inhibition with an increase in concentration of the extracts which indicates that both variables are directly proportional to each other and is in agreement with Esimone *et al.*, (1998), who reported that extract of plants inhibit the growth of various microorganisms at different concentrations. This is synonymous to the results of this study where

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